

Four-dimensional spinor representations of the Lorentz group: Eight-component Dirac spinor with extra degrees of freedom that can be associated with isospin

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Introduction: Spinor representations of the Lorentz group

Let L be an element of $SL(2, \mathbb{C})$ and let X be a spinor associated with a 4-vector x^μ

$$X = x^\mu \sigma_\mu = \begin{pmatrix} t + z & x - iy \\ x + iy & t - z \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

σ_0 is the identity and σ_i are the Pauli matrices. In terms of complex parameters α^μ , L also can be written as $L = \alpha^\mu \sigma_\mu$:

$$L = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 + \alpha_3 & \alpha_1 - i\alpha_2 \\ \alpha_1 + i\alpha_2 & \alpha_0 - \alpha_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Definition of α_μ in terms of boost and rotation parameters is given in the Appendix.

x^μ transforms as $x^\mu \rightarrow x'^\mu = \Lambda x^\mu$, where Λ is the 4×4 real Lorentz transformation matrix, and X transforms as

$$X \rightarrow X' = LXL^\dagger \quad (3)$$

where X' corresponds to x'^μ .

Let us assume that x^μ is a null 4-vector, i.e. $\det X = 0$, then we can write X as an outer product of 2-component spinors ω

$$X = \omega\omega^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix} (u^* \quad v^*) = \begin{pmatrix} uu^* & uv^* \\ vu^* & vv^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $uu^* = t + z$, $uv^* = x - iy$, $vu^* = x + iy$, $vv^* = t - z$ and ω transforms as

$$\omega \rightarrow \omega' = L\omega \quad (5)$$

Now we are looking for a 4-component spinor representation of the Lorentz group. For this purpose we define 4×4 version of the Pauli matrices that can be obtained by the following extension, where we choose a particular transformation of the basis, $A(\dots)A^{-1}$, in order to make a direct connection with the 4×4 real Lorentz transformation matrix Λ :

$$\Sigma_\mu = A(\sigma_\mu \otimes \sigma_0)A^{-1} \quad (6)$$

$$A = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i & -i & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad A^{-1} = A^\dagger \quad (7)$$

$$\Sigma_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \Sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \Sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & i \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \Sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Σ_i obeys the same commutation relations as σ_i , $[\Sigma_i, \Sigma_j] = 2i\epsilon_{ijk}\Sigma_k$.

Similarly we define a 4×4 matrix Z which is an extended version of L :

$$Z = A(L \otimes \sigma_0)A^{-1} \quad (9)$$

In terms of α_μ , Z can be written as

$$Z = \alpha^\mu \Sigma_\mu = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 & \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_1 & \alpha_0 & -i\alpha_3 & i\alpha_2 \\ \alpha_2 & i\alpha_3 & \alpha_0 & -i\alpha_1 \\ \alpha_3 & -i\alpha_2 & i\alpha_1 & \alpha_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

We also define a matrix $Q = A(X \otimes I)A^{-1}$ as an extended version of X :

$$Q = x^\mu \Sigma_\mu = \begin{pmatrix} t & x & y & z \\ x & t & -iz & iy \\ y & iz & t & -ix \\ z & -iy & ix & t \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

In accordance with Eq.(3), Q transforms as

$$Q \rightarrow Q' = ZQZ^\dagger \quad (12)$$

In general, $\det Q \neq 0$ and Q can be associated with x^μ which may not be a null 4-vector. Hence Q' corresponds to $x'^\mu = \Lambda x^\mu$ for any x^μ . But, for the moment let us assume that $\det Q = 0$ and Q corresponds to a null 4-vector. How far can we pursue the analogy with the 2-component spinor representation that is given in Eqs.(4)-(5)? In other words, can we write Q as an outer product, $Q = \zeta\zeta^\dagger$, where ζ transform as $\zeta \rightarrow \zeta' = Z\zeta$? The answer is yes. There exists an object ζ consisting of a pair of 4-component spinors. Here we represent ζ as a 4×2 matrix:

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u & v \\ v & u \\ -iv & iu \\ u & -v \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Actually, each column of ζ can be regarded independently as a 4-component spinor but only the two column spinor pair ζ is directly related to x^μ via the outer product $Q = \zeta\zeta^\dagger$:

$$Q = \zeta\zeta^\dagger = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} uu^* + vv^* & uv^* + vu^* & iuv^* - ivu^* & uu^* - vv^* \\ vu^* + uv^* & vv^* + uu^* & ivv^* - iuu^* & vu^* - uv^* \\ -ivu^* + iuv^* & -ivv^* + iuu^* & vv^* + uu^* & -ivu^* - iuv^* \\ uu^* - vv^* & uv^* - vu^* & iuv^* + ivu^* & uu^* + vv^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} t & x & y & z \\ x & t & -iz & iy \\ y & iz & t & -ix \\ z & -iy & ix & t \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Furthermore, ζ transforms as

$$\zeta \rightarrow \zeta' = Z\zeta \quad (15)$$

In this representation, a 4×4 real Lorentz transformation matrix can be factorized as [1,2]

$$\Lambda = ZZ^* = Z^*Z \quad (16)$$

where, by definition

$$Z^* = A(\sigma_0 \otimes L^*)A^{-1} \quad (17)$$

Therefore, Eq.(16) is equivalent to

$$\Lambda = A(L \otimes L^*)A^{-1} \quad (18)$$

Four-component Weyl spinors in four-dimensional vector space: Doubling the number of massless fermions

We define 4×4 version of $\sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}$ in terms of Σ_i given in Eq.(8):

$$\Sigma \cdot \mathbf{n} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & n_1 & n_2 & n_3 \\ n_1 & 0 & -in_3 & in_2 \\ n_2 & in_3 & 0 & -in_1 \\ n_3 & -in_2 & in_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

where $\Sigma = (\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2, \Sigma_3)$ and $\mathbf{n} = (\sin \theta \cos \phi, \sin \theta \sin \phi, \cos \theta)$. $\Sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}$ is a traceless Hermitian matrix and it has four orthogonal eigenvectors:

$$\psi_R = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ -iv \\ u \end{pmatrix}, \quad \psi_L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} v^* \\ -u^* \\ iu^* \\ v^* \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_R = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} v \\ u \\ iu \\ -v \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -u^* \\ v^* \\ iv^* \\ u^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

where $u = \cos(\theta/2)$, $v = \sin(\theta/2)e^{i\phi}$. ψ_R and φ_R correspond to $+1$ and ψ_L and φ_L correspond to -1 eigenvalue. Actually, these are 4-component Weyl spinors, and they are solutions to the following version of the Weyl equations:

$$(\hat{\mathbf{E}} - \Sigma \cdot \hat{\mathbf{p}})\xi = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$(\hat{\mathbf{E}} + \Sigma \cdot \hat{\mathbf{p}})\xi = 0 \quad (22)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{p}} = |\hat{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{n}$. Indeed, the plane wave ansatz for positive and negative energy cases suggest that ψ_R and φ_R are right-chiral, ψ_L and φ_L are left-chiral, particle/antiparticle solutions. Therefore, in the 4-dimensional representation the number of massless fermions is doubled.

$\psi_R, \psi_L, \varphi_R$ and φ_L constitute a basis for 4-dimensional vector space. Left- and right-chiral spinors are related to each other by the spinor metric g :

$$\psi_L = (g\psi_R)^*, \quad \varphi_L = (g\varphi_R)^* \quad (23)$$

where ¹

$$g = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad g^{-1} = g^\dagger \quad (24)$$

Right- and left-chiral spinors transform as

$$\psi_R \rightarrow \psi'_R = Z\psi_R, \quad \varphi_R \rightarrow \varphi'_R = Z\varphi_R \quad (25)$$

$$\psi_L \rightarrow \psi'_L = (Z^{-1})^\dagger \psi_L, \quad \varphi_L \rightarrow \varphi'_L = (Z^{-1})^\dagger \varphi_L \quad (26)$$

Z and $(Z^{-1})^\dagger$ correspond to $(\frac{1}{2}, 0)$ and $(0, \frac{1}{2})$ representations respectively. Z preserves both the spinor metric g and the Minkowski metric η ².

$$Z^T g Z = g, \quad Z^T \eta Z = \eta \quad (27)$$

Since η is real, $Z^T \eta Z = \eta$ directly entails $\Lambda^T \eta \Lambda = \eta$. In an analogy with $\epsilon \sigma_i \epsilon^{-1} = -\sigma_i^*$, we have the following very useful relation:

$$g \Sigma_i g^{-1} = -\Sigma_i^* \quad (28)$$

Mass and two more degrees of freedom with eight-component Dirac spinors

Σ_i matrices anticommute with each other. But Clifford algebra is not possible with Σ_i , because there is no fourth anticommuting matrix. In order to write a Dirac-like equation we have to go to higher dimensions. It can be shown that this is possible with the following extended gamma matrices:

Let us rewrite the Dirac equation with 8×8 G^μ matrices

$$(iG^\mu \partial_\mu - m)\Phi = 0 \quad (29)$$

where

$$G^0 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\Sigma_0 \\ -\Sigma_0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad G^i = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \Sigma_i \\ -\Sigma_i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (30)$$

G^μ obeys the same Clifford algebra as γ^μ

$$\{G^\mu, G^\nu\} = 2\eta^{\mu\nu} \quad (31)$$

¹ 4×4 version of the spinor matrix $\epsilon = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ can be written as $A(\epsilon \otimes \sigma_0)A^{-1} = i\Sigma_2$. However, g is not a trivial extension of ϵ , because $g = i\eta\Sigma_2^*$ where it explicitly involves the mostly minus Minkowski metric η .

²Also, $(Z^{-1})^\dagger$ preserves g and η .

In this Weyl-like basis, Φ is a 8-component spinor that can be split into two 4-component right- and left-chiral spinors. But now we can write Φ in two different ways

$$\Phi_u = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_R \\ \tilde{\psi}_L \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Phi_d = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_R \\ \tilde{\varphi}_L \end{pmatrix} \quad (32)$$

Where each 4-component spinors is of the type given in Eq.(20). Hence, we have positive and negative energy and helicity solutions for Φ_u and Φ_d . This means that, now we have another intrinsic property associated with degrees of freedom denoted by subscripts u and d . It was suggested by Marsch and Narita that these new degrees of freedom can be associated with isospin [3].

Since the Clifford algebra of G^μ and γ^μ is the same, covariance of the Dirac-like equation that given in Eq.(29) can be verified by showing the existence of of a matrix S that satisfies the following property [4]:

$$S^{-1}G^\mu S = \Lambda^\mu_\nu G^\nu \quad (33)$$

The generators of S are given by

$$G^{\mu\nu} = \frac{i}{4}[G^\mu, G^\nu] \quad (34)$$

In the given basis boost and rotation generators are

$$G^{0i} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} -i\Sigma_i & 0 \\ 0 & i\Sigma_i \end{pmatrix}, \quad G^{ij} = \frac{\epsilon_{ijk}}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \Sigma_k & 0 \\ 0 & \Sigma_k \end{pmatrix} \quad (35)$$

Therefore we can write the S matrix in the following form:

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} S_R & 0 \\ 0 & S_L \end{pmatrix} \quad (36)$$

As it is shown in the Appendix

$$S_R = Z, \quad S_L = (Z^{-1})^\dagger \quad (37)$$

Therefore we have the following transformation for Φ_u and Φ_d :

$$\Phi_{u,d} \rightarrow \Phi'_{u,d} = S\Phi_{u,d} \quad (38)$$

Free particle solutions

It is easier to work in Dirac-like basis

$$G_D^0 = \begin{pmatrix} \Sigma_0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\Sigma_0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad G_D^i = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \Sigma_i \\ -\Sigma_i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (39)$$

After applying plane wave ansatz 8×8 Dirac matrix reads

$$\begin{pmatrix} E-m & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -p_x & -p_y & -p_z \\ 0 & E-m & 0 & 0 & -p_x & 0 & ip_z & -ip_y \\ 0 & 0 & E-m & 0 & -p_y & -ip_z & 0 & ip_x \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & E-m & -p_z & ip_y & -ip_x & 0 \\ 0 & p_x & p_y & p_z & -(E+m) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ p_x & 0 & -ip_z & ip_y & 0 & -(E+m) & 0 & 0 \\ p_y & ip_z & 0 & -ip_x & 0 & 0 & -(E+m) & 0 \\ p_z & -ip_y & ip_x & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -(E+m) \end{pmatrix} \Phi_{u,d} = 0 \quad (40)$$

A nontrivial solution exists only if the determinant of the coefficient matrix vanishes

$$\det = (E^2 - \vec{p} \cdot \vec{p} - m^2)^4 = 0 \quad (41)$$

Hence, we have a nontrivial solution only if $E^2 = \vec{p} \cdot \vec{p} + m^2$.

Eq.(40) can be written in a compact form

$$\begin{pmatrix} E - m & -\vec{\Sigma} \cdot \vec{p} \\ \vec{\Sigma} \cdot \vec{p} & -(E + m) \end{pmatrix} \Phi_{u,d} = 0 \quad (42)$$

By using the 4-component spinors as ansatz we obtain free particle solutions for helicity = ± 1 , apart from normalization and phase factors:

$$u_{++} = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_R \\ \frac{|p|}{E+m} \psi_R \end{pmatrix}, \quad u_{+-} = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_L \\ \frac{-|p|}{E+m} \psi_L \end{pmatrix}, \quad u_{-+} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{|p|}{E-m} \psi_R \\ \psi_R \end{pmatrix}, \quad u_{--} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-|p|}{E-m} \psi_L \\ \psi_L \end{pmatrix} \quad (43)$$

where the first subscript denotes energy $\pm$, and the second one denotes helicity ± 1 . Similarly we also have solutions for d_{++}, d_{+-}, d_{-+} and d_{--}

$$d_{++} = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_R \\ \frac{|p|}{E+m} \varphi_R \end{pmatrix}, \quad d_{+-} = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_L \\ \frac{-|p|}{E+m} \varphi_L \end{pmatrix}, \quad d_{-+} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{|p|}{E-m} \varphi_R \\ \varphi_R \end{pmatrix}, \quad d_{--} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-|p|}{E-m} \varphi_L \\ \varphi_L \end{pmatrix} \quad (44)$$

where

$$\psi_R = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta/2) \\ \sin(\theta/2)e^{i\phi} \\ -i \sin(\theta/2)e^{i\phi} \\ \cos(\theta/2) \end{pmatrix}, \quad \psi_L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \sin(\theta/2)e^{-i\phi} \\ -\cos(\theta/2) \\ i \cos(\theta/2) \\ \sin(\theta/2)e^{-i\phi} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_R = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \sin(\theta/2)e^{i\phi} \\ \cos(\theta/2) \\ i \cos(\theta/2) \\ -\sin(\theta/2)e^{i\phi} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -\cos(\theta/2) \\ \sin(\theta/2)e^{-i\phi} \\ i \sin(\theta/2)e^{-i\phi} \\ \cos(\theta/2) \end{pmatrix} \quad (45)$$

For a more general case with spin not aligned with the momentum it is convenient to use ansatz with the component of the spin up or down along the z axis. These ansatz will yield the following free particle solutions:

$$u_{+\uparrow} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ \frac{p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_x + ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{-i(p_x + ip_y)}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_z}{E+m} \end{pmatrix}, \quad u_{+\downarrow} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ -i \\ 0 \\ \frac{p_x - ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{-p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{ip_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_x - ip_y}{E+m} \end{pmatrix}, \quad u_{-\uparrow} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{p_z}{E-m} \\ \frac{p_x + ip_y}{E-m} \\ \frac{-i(p_x + ip_y)}{E-m} \\ \frac{p_z}{E-m} \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad u_{-\downarrow} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{p_x - ip_y}{E-m} \\ \frac{E-m}{-p_z} \\ \frac{E-m}{ip_z} \\ \frac{E-m}{p_x - ip_y} \\ \frac{E-m}{0} \\ 1 \\ -i \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (46)$$

$$d_{+\uparrow} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ i \\ 0 \\ \frac{p_x+ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{ip_z}{E+m} \\ -\frac{(p_x+ip_y)}{E+m} \end{pmatrix}, \quad d_{+\downarrow} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ \frac{-p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_x-ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{i(p_x-ip_y)}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_z}{E+m} \end{pmatrix}, \quad d_{-\uparrow} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{p_x+ip_y}{E-m} \\ \frac{p_z}{E-m} \\ \frac{ip_z}{E-m} \\ -\frac{(p_x+ip_y)}{E-m} \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ i \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad d_{-\downarrow} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-p_z}{E-m} \\ \frac{p_x-ip_y}{E-m} \\ \frac{i(p_x-ip_y)}{E-m} \\ \frac{p_z}{E-m} \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (47)$$

Let us define a Hermitian operator (an observable), D_3 , in the following way:

$$D_3 = \begin{pmatrix} \Sigma_3^* & 0 \\ 0 & \Sigma_3^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (48)$$

The 8-component spinors $u_{+\uparrow}, u_{+\downarrow}, u_{-\uparrow}$ and $u_{-\downarrow}$ are the eigenstates of observable D_3 corresponding to the eigenvalue +1, and $d_{+\uparrow}, d_{+\downarrow}, d_{-\uparrow}$ and $d_{-\downarrow}$ are the eigenstates of D_3 corresponding to the eigenvalue -1.

In general, the generators of the transformations are

$$D_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \Sigma_1^* & 0 \\ 0 & \Sigma_1^* \end{pmatrix}, \quad D_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \Sigma_2^* & 0 \\ 0 & \Sigma_2^* \end{pmatrix}, \quad D_3 = \begin{pmatrix} \Sigma_3^* & 0 \\ 0 & \Sigma_3^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (49)$$

$$\Sigma_1^* = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & i \\ 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Sigma_2^* = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Sigma_3^* = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 \\ 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (50)$$

We define the following ladder operators:

$$D_+ = D_1 - iD_2, \quad D_- = D_1 + iD_2, \quad (51)$$

$$D_+ = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad D_- = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & -i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (52)$$

Action of these operators on the states u_{ij} and d_{ij} ($i = +, -$; $j = \uparrow, \downarrow$) results in the following relations:

$$D_+ u_{ij} = 0, \quad D_+ d_{ij} = u_{ij}, \quad D_- u_{ij} = d_{ij}, \quad D_- d_{ij} = 0 \quad (53)$$

Charge conjugation

For 4-component Dirac spinors charge conjugation operation is given as

$$\Psi^C = \delta C (\bar{\Psi})^T \quad (54)$$

where δ is an arbitrary phase, $C = i\gamma^2\gamma^0$, $\bar{\Psi} = \Psi^\dagger\gamma^0$. Hence in short,

$$\Psi^C = i\gamma^2\Psi^* \quad (55)$$

For 8-component spinors we may suggest an extension of the form

$$\Phi^C = iG^2\Phi^* \quad (56)$$

But it does not work. In order to get the correct form of the charge conjugation we have to introduce Minkowski metric η and write

$$\Phi^C = \mathcal{C}\Phi^* \quad (57)$$

where

$$\mathcal{C} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & i\eta\Sigma_2 \\ -i\eta\Sigma_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (58)$$

$\mathcal{C}$ acts on the 8-component particle/antiparticle states that can be obtained from Eqs.(46) and (47)

$$u_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ \frac{p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_x+ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{E+m}{-i(p_x+ip_y)} \\ \frac{E+m}{p_z} \\ \frac{E+m}{E+m} \end{pmatrix}, \quad u_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ -i \\ 0 \\ \frac{p_x-ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{-p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{ip_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{E+m}{p_x-ip_y} \\ \frac{E+m}{E+m} \end{pmatrix}, \quad v_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{p_x-ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{-p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{ip_z}{E+m} \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ -i \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad v_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_x+ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{E+m}{-i(p_x+ip_y)} \\ \frac{E+m}{p_z} \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (59)$$

$$d_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ i \\ 0 \\ \frac{p_x+ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{ip_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{E+m}{-(p_x+ip_y)} \\ \frac{E+m}{E+m} \end{pmatrix}, \quad d_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ \frac{-p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_x-ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{i(p_x-ip_y)}{E+m} \\ \frac{E+m}{p_z} \\ \frac{E+m}{E+m} \end{pmatrix}, \quad e_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_x-ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{i(p_x-ip_y)}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_z}{E+m} \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad e_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{p_x+ip_y}{E+m} \\ \frac{p_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{ip_z}{E+m} \\ \frac{E+m}{-(p_x+ip_y)} \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ i \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (60)$$

Hence we obtain the following charge conjugation relations:

$$u_1^C = -v_1, \quad u_2^C = v_2, \quad d_1^C = -e_1, \quad d_2^C = e_2 \quad (61)$$

Appendix

Let us begin with the exponential form $Z = e^R$, where $R = -\frac{i}{2}\vec{\pi} \cdot \vec{\Sigma}$, $\pi_i = \theta_i + i\rho_i$, θ and ρ being the rotation and boost parameters respectively. Let ϕ be the complex angle defined as $\phi = \sqrt{\pi_1^2 + \pi_2^2 + \pi_3^2}$. Using the property $R^2 = -\frac{1}{4}\phi^2\Sigma_0$:

$$Z = \cos(\phi/2)\Sigma_0 - \frac{i \sin(\phi/2)}{\phi}\vec{\pi} \cdot \vec{\Sigma} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 & \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_1 & \alpha_0 & -i\alpha_3 & i\alpha_2 \\ \alpha_2 & i\alpha_3 & \alpha_0 & -i\alpha_1 \\ \alpha_3 & -i\alpha_2 & i\alpha_1 & \alpha_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (62)$$

where

$$\alpha_0 = \cos(\phi/2), \quad \alpha_1 = -\frac{i \sin(\phi/2)}{\phi}\pi_1, \quad \alpha_2 = -\frac{i \sin(\phi/2)}{\phi}\pi_2, \quad \alpha_3 = -\frac{i \sin(\phi/2)}{\phi}\pi_3. \quad (63)$$

In compact forms

$$Z = \alpha_0\Sigma_0 + \alpha_1\Sigma_1 + \alpha_2\Sigma_2 + \alpha_3\Sigma_3 \quad (64)$$

$$Z^{-1} = \alpha_0\Sigma_0 - \alpha_1\Sigma_1 - \alpha_2\Sigma_2 - \alpha_3\Sigma_3 \quad (65)$$

$$Z^\dagger = \alpha_0^*\Sigma_0 + \alpha_1^*\Sigma_1 + \alpha_2^*\Sigma_2 + \alpha_3^*\Sigma_3 \quad (66)$$

$$(Z^{-1})^\dagger = \alpha_0^*\Sigma_0 - \alpha_1^*\Sigma_1 - \alpha_2^*\Sigma_2 - \alpha_3^*\Sigma_3 \quad (67)$$

The corresponding L matrices are

$$L = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 + \alpha_3 & \alpha_1 - i\alpha_2 \\ \alpha_1 + i\alpha_2 & \alpha_0 - \alpha_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (68)$$

In compact forms

$$L = \alpha_0\sigma_0 + \alpha_1\sigma_1 + \alpha_2\sigma_2 + \alpha_3\sigma_3 \quad (69)$$

$$L^{-1} = \alpha_0\sigma_0 - \alpha_1\sigma_1 - \alpha_2\sigma_2 - \alpha_3\sigma_3 \quad (70)$$

$$L^\dagger = \alpha_0^*\sigma_0 + \alpha_1^*\sigma_1 + \alpha_2^*\sigma_2 + \alpha_3^*\sigma_3 \quad (71)$$

$$(L^{-1})^\dagger = \alpha_0^*\sigma_0 - \alpha_1^*\sigma_1 - \alpha_2^*\sigma_2 - \alpha_3^*\sigma_3 \quad (72)$$

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